

PEER ASSESSMENT AS A TOOL FOR COLLABORATIVE LEARNING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Peer assessment has become an increasingly remarkable role in the field of English teaching and as modern pedagogy emphasizes the value of active and collaborative learning in the schools. According to my experience, I used to use traditional assessment methods, where I was an only evaluator of students' work who created a passive learning environment. Students often see grades not as learning opportunity they accept it as external judgment. This case has created a demand for innovative approaches that encourage students to play an active participation in evaluating and reflecting on their tasks. This approach is one such strategy, as it engages students to learn how to give and receive feedback, develops critical thinking, and strengthens a classroom culture based on dialogue, reflection, and shared responsibility.

This article is aimed to analyze a peer assessment method as a tool for collaborative learning and to present both theoretical and practical applications of this method. The main research question is how peer assessment can provide to students' language development, motivation, and responsibility. My research shows that this method supports students' autonomy, improves higher-order thinking skills, and nourishes cooperation within the class. In Topping's research (2009) clarifies peer assessment as a process in which students evaluate the quality of their work based on assessment criteria, while Falchikov and Goldfinch (2000), in their popular meta-analysis, show that peer evaluations often correlate strongly with teacher grades when rubrics and training are provided. Boud and Molloy (2013) highlight that feedback must not be perceived as a one-way transmission from teacher to student, but rather as an interactive process set in students' practices. Liu and Carless (2006) include that peer feedback in the classrooms is particularly valuable for writing and speaking, as it raises awareness of accuracy, organization, and communicative effectiveness.

Despite these advantages, peer assessment was challenging for my students. Students felt insecure about assessing their classmates, they may doubt the fairness of the process, or they may lack the knowledge to apply assessment criteria objectively. In many situations, students are also suspicious to criticize peers, fearing that it could damage social relationships. Furthermore, not all students are skilled enough in giving constructive feedback, and some may dismiss peer comments in favor of teacher evaluation. These matters showed me that my students need structured preparation, clear rubrics, and continuous teacher guidance in order to build confidence while giving constructive evaluation.

In my own teaching practice, I integrated peer assessment into two groups of intermediate-language level students of 11th grade. The project continued eight weeks integrating writing and speaking activities, which provided different contexts for peer evaluation. At the preparation stage, I explained to students the purpose of peer assessment and its benefits for learning. We discussed how to give supportive but critical comments, and I designed a rubric that included criteria such as fluency, accuracy, vocabulary use, organization, and clarity of ideas. In addition, I organized short training sessions where students analyzed sample answers and practiced giving comments in pairs. This practice reduced anxiety and gradually made them more confident in using the method.

During the implementation stage, I applied peer assessment in two main forms. For writing tasks, students wrote essays and then exchanged them with a partner. Each student was asked to underline strengths in the text and suggest at least two areas for improvement, guided by the rubric. This ensured that the feedback was balanced and constructive. For speaking tasks, students prepared pair presentations, while the audience used checklists to evaluate aspects such as fluency, vocabulary range, and pronunciation. After each presentation, classmates shared their feedback orally, and I supplemented it with my own comments. In both cases, the activity concluded with a reflection stage:

learners wrote short self-reports where they compared peer and teacher feedback and noted what they planned to improve in future tasks. This final step was especially important, as it encouraged students not only to receive comments but also to process them and set concrete goals.

The results of this practice were multifaceted. First, students' engagement increased significantly. They became more attentive listeners and more careful writers, knowing that their work would be reviewed by their classmates. Second, they developed greater awareness of assessment criteria, which students began to apply spontaneously when they start working on new tasks. For example, several students reported that while writing essays, they thought about organization more consciously because they knew it would be evaluated. Third, the sense of collaboration in the classroom improved. Students expressed that they felt they were learning with and from one another, not only competing for grades.

Additionally, some of them initially provided only very positive comments, avoiding criticism. They feared that honest remarks might harm their relationships with classmates. To address this, I modeled examples of balanced feedback and provided sentence starters such as "*One strong point is... but one thing you could improve is...*". Over time, this practice helped students see critical feedback as supportive rather than negative. Stronger students tended to give detailed feedback, while weaker ones limited themselves to vague statements such as "*good job.*" To address this, I paired students strategically and reminded them to rely strictly on the rubric. I also monitored their comments and discussed examples of effective and ineffective feedback in class.

Time management was another challenge. Peer assessment sessions required more classroom time than traditional teacher feedback, particularly in the early stages when students were still learning the process. To solve this, I planned shorter but more frequent peer assessment tasks, allowing students to practice regularly without overwhelming the lesson structure. As students became more experienced, the sessions became quicker and more efficient. Another issue concerned the acceptance of peer feedback. At first, some learners paid little attention to their classmates' comments, considering teacher feedback the only valid authority. To change this perception, I highlighted instances where student comments coincided with my own evaluations, showing that their observations were accurate and meaningful. I also encouraged learners to write reflections about what they learned specifically from peer feedback that they had not noticed before. These activities gradually increased the credibility of peer assessment in their eyes.

Overall, the application of peer assessment in my classroom confirmed its value as a tool for collaborative learning. It enhanced not only students' language skills but also their capacity for reflection, analysis, and cooperation. Importantly, it shifted the classroom dynamic from teacher-centered to learner-centered, giving students more responsibility for their progress. The process also promoted a sense of community, as students supported one another's development rather than viewing assessment as a purely competitive exercise.

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